

Linguistic Comparison in Vocabulary for Japanese to Understand Okinawan

Shuhei Miyairi

Okinawa Christian School International, Yomitan, Okinawa, Japan

ABSTRACT

The goal of this research is to compare the differences and similarities in the vocabulary between Okinawan and Japanese, which are the two most spoken Japonic languages. Both languages are still alive to this day. This will use the 索引篇(標準語引き) database created by the National Language Research Institute and compare it by using the point class system described by Beaufils' eLinguistics.net's sound correspondence, which are integer values of 0, 70, 85, 95, or 100. This method has been chosen because vowels change more rapidly than consonants (Beaufils, 2023). Then, it was computed using the R code created by the author to determine the mutual intelligibility between the two languages. On average, the Okinawan words are 39.34638% similar to Japanese but vary based on the criteria and metric. This research is significant because it has provided insight into multiple perspectives on the quantitative differences between Okinawan and Japanese vocabularies. Depending on the calculation method, the value for mutual intelligibility differs.

Keywords: *Okinawan-Ryukyuan, Japonic, Japanese, mutual intelligibility, statistical linguistics, R code*

1. INTRODUCTION

Okinawan is among the six Ryukyuan languages and is endangered by UNESCO's standards (Miyara, 2018). Early Proto-Ryukyuan speakers migrated southward to the Ryukyuan islands through various periods up to about the 13th century (Pellard, 2011, pp. 61). They remained isolated from any other contact until the Satsuma invasion in the 17th century (Shimoji & Pellard, 2010, pp. 4).

In recent years, while Okinawan is known to be uncommonly used, it can be challenged when looking at some signs, such as those covered in Heinrich's research and place names (Heinreich, 2016, pp. 333). For example, the restaurant 鶴小(ちるぐわー)(chirugwaa) is a good example of this (そば家 鶴小, 2016). The word chirugwaa combines the Okinawan word for crane (chiru) and the diminutive (gwaa); therefore, it means little crane or baby crane.

The number of native speakers is unknown and varies from source to source, which ranges between 95,000 and almost a million (University of Hawaii at Manoa, 2024). Many Ryukyuan language speakers are now bilingual in Japanese; for example, all living Ikema Miyakoan speakers are bilingual in Ikema Miyakoan and Japanese (Shinohara & Hussain, pp. 242). However, according to recent surveys as of 2023, about 3.8% of Okinawans use it more than Japanese and 11.6% use it as equally as Japanese, which means that a total of 15.4% of Okinawans use Okinawan as much or more than they use Japanese (Okinawa Prefectural Government, 2024). This means that there are still some people who use Okinawan far more than Japanese. Therefore, it is still worth investigating Okinawan and comparing it with Japanese.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Aim of the study

By quantifying the similarities and differences in the vocabulary between Okinawan and Japanese, Japanese speakers interested in learning Okinawan would be able to determine the difficulty of the language and can judge for themselves whether it is an ideal language for them to learn.

In addition, it will help understand if the Japonic languages are similar to those of other language families, such as Romance and Slavic languages (Pellard, 2018). It will determine if the Ryukyuan languages are about as different as Romance languages, or more or less.

Some may argue that research has shown that Oki-No-Erabu cannot understand Ikema speakers and Ikema speakers can understand virtually almost nothing in Oki-No-Erabu (Takubo, 2018).

However, neither Oki-No-Erabu nor Ikema, a dialect of Miyakoan, is widely spoken. Therefore, this study will look at two of the largest Japonic languages, Japanese and Okinawan, and compare the two languages by their similarities in vocabulary.

It is expected that the similarity between Okinawan and Japanese is about 70-71% based on previous research estimates made in the past (Heinrich, 2022; Lithoco, 2020). However, since there may be a difference in calculation methods, there may be some deviation, but it is highly unlikely that it will differ by a significant margin.

2.2 Research Design

The Ryukyuan languages are often tied with the Japonic languages. However, how much Japanese speakers can understand the Ryukyuan language remains a mystery. To answer this question quantitatively, this research paper will use the point class system described by Beaufils' eLinguistics.net's sound correspondence, since consonants are the backbones of words and vowels can change much more easily than consonants (Beaufils, 2023).

Each letter will be aligned and measured using R. The word for bird in Japonic languages is useful for demonstrating the methodology. To give a sample, the example will use Japanese, a northern Ryukyuan language called Okinawan, and two southern Ryukyuan languages called Miyakoan and the Ishigaki dialect of Yaeyama (Shimoji, 2022). The words for each of these languages respectively are とり (tori), とうい (tui), とうイ° (tuɪ) or とうす° (tusɪ), and とうりう or とうる (turu) (Cambridge University Press & Assessment, 1995; Celik, 2022; Sakihara, 2006; Shimakutuba Promotion Center, 2024a; Shimakutuba Promotion Center, 2024b; Shimakutuba Promotion Center, 2024c; Shimakutuba Promotion Center et al., 2021; Shimoji, 2022). Since the consonants of Yaeyama (Ishigaki dialect) are similar to the Japanese word in this case, if these words were inputted into the program, it would determine that when only looking at the word for bird, the words are a perfect match based solely on consonants. Only the consonants will be looked at because consonants are the backbones of any word out there since vowels can easily change relative to consonants (Beaufils, 2023). This will be done for the entire database used to determine the similarities between the two languages based on vocabulary.

2.3 Sample

The 索引篇(標準語引き) database created by the National Language Research Institute will be used for comparing Japanese with Okinawan. The database consists of the Okinawan equivalents of Japanese words.

2.4 Scales Used

This study will use the point class system in the updated new model made by Beaufils from May 2023. As of the latest data, each consonant combination is numerically assigned an integer of 0, 70, 85, 95, or 100 (perfect match). Sound consonance of lexical similarity will be used for mutual intelligibility (see Appendix for more details).

For analysis, this study used R to calculate the statistics necessary. All code was written from scratch.

2.5 Data Collection Procedure

The data analysis algorithm was created by converting the Japanese hiragana into the matching romaji, then making sure it correctly matched the letters used in the Okinawan words by ensuring that all consonants were the same. For example, the initial glottal stop, represented by an apostrophe, was converted to Q to match the other glottal stops. Using the measures mentioned earlier, the algorithm would calculate the average for each Japanese word represented in the list `avList`, and do the minimum and maximum similarity variations by adding them into `minList` and `maxList` respectively. In other words, `minList` is when an Okinawan speaker intentionally uses the least similar word to the Japanese word all the time, whereas the `maxList` is when an Okinawan speaker intentionally uses the most similar word to the Japanese word all the time. Then, after the data was analyzed, the mean and standard deviation were calculated and graphs were made accordingly. Additionally, medians, IQR, density function with Silverman's rule of thumb, and the relative frequency of `minList` and `maxList` will be graphed. The reason for the last aforementioned graph is that `minList` and `maxList` are not represented well with a density function because the values will be exact; i.e., within the data values in the two lists, there are only contain data that have possible data in Beaufils' eLinguistics.net's sound correspondence. All samples that cannot be processed from the coded program will be omitted from the 10232 Japanese words provided in the dataset.

3. RESULTS

In the end, 193 samples were removed because they were not processable. The other 10039 samples were calculated using the methodology above.

Figure 1 shows that the average overall is 39.34638% similar to Japanese with a standard deviation of 34.9766%. If Okinawan speakers intentionally used the least similar Okinawan word possible to Japanese, it lowers down to 28.03527% with a standard deviation of 44.46682%. If

Okinawan speakers intentionally used the most similar Okinawan word to Japanese, it goes up to 68.37858% with a standard deviation of 45.59722%.

Figure 1: *Percentage of Okinawan Vocabulary that is Mutually Intelligible for Japanese speakers (Mean and Standard Deviation)*

Note. minList is intentionally using the least similar Okinawan word choice to Japanese, maxList is intentionally using the most similar Okinawan word choice to Japanese, and avList is using it as average as possible. All calculations are based on the sound consonance of lexical similarity.

Figure 2 shows that, that overall median is 33.33333, and consisted of many zeros and 100s based on the median of the two other lists. The IQR of the overall list is 66.66667, and the IQR of the other two are 100.

Figure 2: *Percentage of Okinawan Vocabulary that is Mutually Intelligible for Japanese speakers (Median and IQR)*

Note. minList is intentionally using the least similar Okinawan word choice to Japanese, maxList is intentionally using the most similar Okinawan word choice to Japanese, and avList is using it as average as possible. All calculations are based on the sound consonance of lexical similarity. Figure 3b is closer to Figure 3a than Figure 3c, which means that the average is likely to be closer to the average of minList than maxList. The main difference in the shape of the graphs between Figure 3a and Figure 3b is that Figure 3b tends to have more probability in the values in the middle.

Figure 3: Probability distribution within ± 1 that Japanese Speakers Can Understand Okinawan By Relative Frequency (Silverman's Rule of Thumb)

Note. minList is intentionally using the least similar Okinawan word choice to Japanese, maxList is intentionally using the most similar Okinawan word choice to Japanese, and avList is using it as average as possible. All calculations are based on the sound consonance of lexical similarity. When comparing Figures 4 and 5, there are more zeros in minList (0.715) than 100s in maxList (0.626) by relative frequencies, which shows that there are more dissimilar consonants than similar consonants in the sample.

Figure 4: *Histogram of Maximum Similarity for Variation of Words for Japanese Speakers to Understand Okinawan*

Note. maxList is intentionally using the most similar Okinawan word choice to Japanese.

Figure 5: *Histogram of Minimum Similarity for Variation of Words for Japanese Speakers to Understand Okinawan*

Note. minList is intentionally using the least similar Okinawan word choice to Japanese.

4. DISCUSSION

Based on the results, it is less similar than languages such as the similarity between Spanish and Portuguese, which is 89%, but more than the difference between English and French, which is 27% (Garcia & de Souza, 2014). That was expected. However, it was not expected that Okinawan and Japanese were less similar than expected relative to the 70-71% in the hypothesis. The mean is a little under 40% and even the closest variations of possible Okinawan words were 68%, which does not quite hit the mark of 70-71% of the initial hypothesis. The least similar variation of the Okinawan word relative to Japanese is about 28%. In comparison, the similarity between French and German is 29% (Racoma, 2019). This places the least similar variation of the Okinawan word relative to Japanese right in between the similarity between English and French, and the similarity between French and German. Therefore, it could be argued that Okinawan and Japanese are from separate language families.

In fact, according to Ethnologue, Ryukyuan languages are a subgroup under Japonic (SIL International, 2024). But at the very least, they should be considered different languages as it is less similar than Romanian and Spanish (Fan et al., 2021).

However, linguistic similarity cannot be easily determined. In this case, the 2 standard deviation error bars for all lists contained all values between 0 and 100 inclusive. This is because lexical similarity cannot be clearly defined. However, based on metrics, values mentioned in this research can give a general idea of how similar the vocabularies of the languages are relative to others.

Furthermore, more variations of Okinawan translations for Japanese words differ than being similar or the same based on the data in the results provided earlier.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this methodology can be applied across all Ryukyuan languages. Because many words in Japonic languages tend to have the same consonants, it will help compare the vocabularies with different consonant combinations. Other language families that have the same consonant combinations should use the same methodology to calculate a value for determining mutual intelligibility.

In the future, a comparison between multiple Ryukyuan languages or any other language family can be further explored. Another potential future research is increasing the sample from approximately 10,000 words used for this research to the number of words in Japanese. While there are no one-to-one approximations for every Japanese word in Okinawan, increasing the sample size may have more accurate results. Currently, Japanese has about 500,000 words (Andrew, 2023). Therefore, the current sample size only accounts for 2% of all Japanese words available.

A third potential future research topic is comparing Okinawan with Old Japanese. There is a preliminary study done between Old Okinawan and Old Japanese from a grammatical standpoint (Shinzato, 2015). However, a comprehensive study between Modern Okinawan and Old Japanese is still worth investigating with a possible control group of Modern Japanese. This is because Okinawans have the highest concentration of Jomon blood out of the people in Japan (Liu et al., 2024). However, in contrast to the Old Japanese-speaking Jomon people, early-modern Okinawans have a flatter nasal root (Fukusae, 2012). This may relate to the Okinawan language using the letter N (IPA /ŋ/), which is neither Japanese nor Old Japanese has.

While written down it does not differ from the normal *n* (ん), they are distinctive pronunciations, which may be because of changes in genomes over time. Potentially, after a comparison between linguistics, research can be conducted based on the linguistic correlations to the alterations of phenotypes between Old Japanese, Modern Japanese, and Modern Okinawan people.

Furthermore, this research is significant because it has provided insight into multiple perspectives on the quantitative differences between Okinawan and Japanese vocabularies. Depending on the calculation method, the value for mutual intelligibility differs.

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Appendix

The correlation scores are assigned based on Beaufils' values. T represents the ts as in 月 (**tsuki** in Japanese, and non-existent in standard Okinawan). Lowercase c represents the ch sound as in 茶 (**cha** in Japanese and **chaa** in Okinawan). Uppercase C represents the h in the hiragana ひ as in 火 (**hi** in Japanese and **hii** in Okinawan). This sound differs from ha, fu, he, and ho because it is represented with the IPA /ç/. Uppercase S represents the sh as in 石 (**ishi** in Japanese and **shii** in Okinawan). N exists solely in Okinawan in words such as ぬかい (Nkai), which is represented by the IPA /ŋ/. All other consonants are written accordingly with the romaji representation of Japanese and Okinawan words.

Japanese	Okinawan	Correlation Score
b	b	100
b	p	95
b	w	70
b	f	85
b	v	85
T	T	100
T	c	85
T	t	85
T	d	70
T	z	70
T	s	70
T	S	70
c	c	100
c	T	85
c	t	85
c	d	70

c	z	70
c	S	70
c	j	85
d	d	100
d	t	95
d	s	85
d	z	85
d	S	85
d	c	70
d	T	70
f	f	100
f	v	95
f	p	85
f	b	85
g	g	100
g	k	95
g	C	85
g	h	85
g	j	85
h	h	100
h	C	95
h	k	85
h	g	85
j	j	100

j	S	95
j	z	85
j	s	85
j	t	85
j	g	85
j	c	85
k	k	100
k	g	95
k	C	85
k	h	85
C	C	100
C	r	95
C	h	95
C	k	85
C	g	85
m	m	100
n	n	100
p	p	100
p	b	95
p	f	85
p	v	85

r	r	100
r	C	95
s	s	100
s	t	85
s	d	85
s	T	70
s	S	70
s	j	85
s	z	70
S	S	100
S	j	95
S	t	85
S	d	85
S	c	70
S	T	70
S	s	70
S	z	70
t	t	100
t	d	95
t	s	85
t	z	85
t	S	85
t	c	85
t	T	85

t	j	85
v	v	100
v	f	95
v	p	85
v	w	70
v	b	85
w	b	70
w	w	100
w	v	70
z	z	100
z	s	95
z	t	85
z	d	85
z	c	70
z	T	70
z	j	85
z	S	85